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Recently used nanocatalysts in reduction of nitroarenes

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Abstract

Nanocatalysis is swiftly mounting in various catalyzed organic reactions. Nowadays a wide variety of nano sized species such as nanoparticles or nanocomposites are effectively employed as catalyst. Conventionally noble metals such as Pt, Pd, Rh and Au are used in various heterogeneous catalytic reductions in organic chemistry. Heterogeneous hydrogenation catalysis is highly desirable since in this stage the important enantio-differentiating step is happening at the metal surface. In this review, we try to underscore the recent development of using the traditional noble metals in their nano forms as nanocatalysts in the reduction of nitroarenes such as 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) and related compounds to their corresponding amino derivatives.

Keyword

Metal nanoparticles, Nanocatalysts, Nitroarenes, Reduction reaction